

Empowerment of Creative Economy to Improve Community Incomes in Takalar Regency

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Abstract: *The study aims to examine the role of creative economy in increasing community incomes, as well as its contribution to Gross Regional Product, and reviewing the type of creative economy developed to improve people's income. This study will be conducted in 9 districts in Takalar. Data collection techniques conducted with observation, interview, documentation, questionnaires, and Focus Group Discussion. The research population all of the creative industries of Small Medium Enterprises in Takalar during the year of 2011-2012. The sampling technique is determined in random by using proportion estimation sampling repetition (sampling without replacement) by setting the error rate of 5%. The method of analysis used in this study are: Validity and Reliability Test of Research Instruments and Descriptive Analysis. The results of this study: 1) creative economy or the creative industries have prospective potential to be developed and managed professionally, not only as an activity on a small scale home industry but also as a leading sector in Takalar Regency. 2) Takalar Regency has various creative industries which highly potential to be developed through intensive training, it is evident from the spread of types of creative industries in every district, each of which is characterized by excellent products in the field of creative industrie. 3) The production value of the creative industries sector from year to year continues to increase, however its contribution to the total production of goods and services in Takalar still relatively small at only about 6.94% per year. This means that the government Takalar Regency through relevant agencies have not seriously make efforts to arrange and guide of creative economics intensively, which is potential to absorb more labor and support increase public revenues.*

I. Introduction

The term of creative industries became more popular. Yet the understanding of this industry is still vague for most people. However thus need to be understood that the creative industry is a derivation of the creative economy. Creative activities related to innovative businesses that offer the discovery of science and technology (IPTEK) and the application of science and technology for product improvement and new creations, new tools, new methods, and new technologies that can meet the needs of the market; including those relating to the humanities such as linguistics development research and development, literature and art as well as business and management consultancy services (Pangestu; 2005).

Basically creative economic growth is driven by the capitalization of creativity and innovation in providing products or services with creative content. The keyword is high creative content toward input and output of these economic activities. The term of creative economy is still relatively new. Not surprisingly that the understanding has not been defined clearly. In general it can be said that the creative economy is a system of human activities related to the creation, production, distribution, exchange, and consumption of goods and services that are valuable by cultural, artistic, aesthetic, intellectual, and emotional for the customers in the market..

Indonesian government specifically the Ministry of Trade, is closer to the classification used by Howkins (2001). We have successfully mapped the creative industries sector, among others: (1) advertising, (2) architecture (3) art and antiques market, (4) crafts, (5) design, (6) fashion, (7) video, film, and photography, (8) interactive games, (9) music, (10) performing arts, (11) publishing and printing, (12) computer services and software, (13) television and radio, and (14) research and development. The Minister of Trade Mari Elka Pangestu said that the contribution of the creative economy around 4.75% of GDP in 2006 (about Rp 170 trillion) and 7% of total exports in 2006. Creative economic growth reached 7.3% in 2006, higher than the national growth rate of 5.6%. The economic sector is also able to absorb about 3.7 million workers which equivalent to 4.7% of total new employment. Seven biggest contributors are (1) fashion with a contribution of 29.85%, (2) Craft with a contribution of 18.38%, and (3) advertising with a contribution of 18.38%, (4) television and radio, (5) architecture, (6) music, and (7) publishing and printing.

Based on data from the Ministry of Trade Republic of Indonesia, it shows that creative industries contribute significantly to the national GDP with average of 2002-2006 amounted to 104.637 trillion or moving with an average growth of 6.28%. In terms of employee absorption, the creative industries 2002-2006 period reached 5.4 million workers, or 5.79% of the entire workforce in Indonesia.

Observing the fact that occur nationally, it can be interpreted that creative industry is a sector of economic activities that is prospective for development when viewed from the side of income and employment absorption. Therefore, the development of creative industries needs serious attention in order to develop social creativity and in turn will encourage the public revenue

Takalar Regency is one of the regions that intensively developing it's economy. This is shown by the economic growth in 2007 amounted to 6.04% and in 2011 the economic growth reached 7.24%. However, the poverty level in 2007 amounted to 13.60% and 11.02% in 2011. This indicates that economic growth has not significantly influence the level of poverty in the Takalar Regency. To reduce poverty it is necessary to increase community revenue through economic empowerment of the creative economy which is supported by economic potential in Takalar.

One of potential sectors to be developed to overcome unemployment and low income levels are the creative industries. The potential of creative industries of Takalar Regency likely to increase welfare and create jobs by generating and exploiting the creativity and inventiveness of individual craftsmen. This is because the region has been well known as center of traditional ceramic craft industry and has been in the long process to become part of traditional ceramics existence which managed for generations. Moreover, people in this area have long wrestle in small-scale industries activities that rely on innovation and creativity such as the manufacture of woven from pandanus leaves, bamboo, woven palm fiber, boat building, brick, and the last that much developed is the processing of seaweed.

Results of preliminary observations conducted by researchers, it is obtained that in every district can actually be used as centers of certain craft because between one district with another, each has a different characteristic. This potential certainly provides a great opportunity especially if it can be coupled with tourism activities. The integration between creative industries sector with tourism sector become the entrance of intensive development and training activities. The problem then is, data collection and industries searching efforts that utilize the creativity and inventiveness of society in Takalar are not optimal. In addition, there is no connectivity between supporting tourism sector. The development of tourism sector is relatively separated, and not implemented integratively with the development of creative industries areas, whereas these two sectors can be mutually supportive. Another thing that has not been done is still minimal coaching activities. Management of production activities for creative industries is still managed traditionallu, have not yet maximize the potential use of technology and creativity and imagination which are more modern.

II. Issues

1. How the role of creative economy in improving community income in Takalar Regency.
2. What kind of creative economy that can improve community income of Takalar Regency.
3. What is the value of creative economy contribution to Gross Domestic Product of Takalar Regency.

III. Goals and Objectives

1. Research Objectives
 - a. This research aims to review how the role of creative economy in improving community income, as well as it's contribution to Gross Regional Product.
 - b. To review the type of creative economy which developed to increase community income
2. Research Goals
 - a. To review the role of creative economy in improving community income
 - b. To identify the contribution of creative economy on gros regional domestic product.
 - c. To identify the types of creative economics that can be developed to improve community income.

IV. Conceptual Framework

Creative Industry is an industrial subsectors which in the current era is seen as an economic activities that is highly potential and prospective to be developed in promoting economic growth and increase community income who are actively involve in Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Creative industry development goals based on Presidential Decree No. 6 of 2009 are; insane creatively with creative mindset, superior industry in domestic and international markets, the technology that supports the creation of creative and affordable by community, the use of domestic raw materials effectively, with the hope that in order to realize; increasing number of qualified creative human resource sustainably and equally distibuted across Indonesia, improvement and development of quality of formal and informal education and training institutions which support creative insane in the development of creative economy, an increasing number of creative entrepreneurship as economic powerhouse in the field of creative industries.

Source: Elaborated from various sources, Research Team 2013

V. Research Methodology

This research will be conducted in Takalar Regency in 9 districts. To obtain data, the steps and techniques used are survey, observation, interviews, documentation, questionnaires, and Focus Group Discussion. Type of data used is qualitative data in the form of respondents and government questionnaire interview results, and the quantitative data obtained from the Department of Industry, Trade and Mines, Regional Planning and Development Board of Takalar, and the Central Bureau of Statistics Takalar.

Research population is all the Small medium enterprise creative industries in Takalar years 2011-20012. The techniques used for sampling is determined randomly by using the formula of proportion estimation sampling without repetition sampling (sampling without replacement) by setting the error rate of 5% (Daniel and Terrel, 1989). The method of analysis used in this study are: Research Instruments Validity and Reliability Tests as well as Descriptive Analysis

VI. Research Results

1. Condition of Creative Industry Sector in Takalar Regency

Industrial companies in Takalar in 2010 are 2,230 with the number of workforces up to 7,255. These numbers are not increase from previous year where the number of companies and workforces are noted 2,230 and 7,255 respectively. The details can be shown below:

2. Mangarabombang District

Mangarabombang District area is 100.50 km² width including 12 villages with 36,724 population and 8,446 households in 2010 and the population density was 365 people km².

Table 1 Number of Creative Industries in Mangarabombang District in 2010 – 2011

Industry Type	2010		2011	
	Units	Workforces	Units	Workforces
Brown Sugar Production	1	27	1	10
Lunkhead (dodol) Production	3	30	3	25
Salt Production	189	417	170	380
Salt Iodine Compounding	15	150	6	35
Gedogan Weaving	58	78	20	36
Bamboo plaiting	6	6	2	8
Pandanous leaves plaiting	209	329	209	329
Bricks production	4	42	4	36
Blacksmiths	22	83	22	83
Palmyra leaves plaiting	32	37	32	46
Shrimp Paste Production	39	110	39	110
Mixed Asphalt	0	0	1	15
Motorcycle workshop	3	18	14	52
Wooden carpenter	6	17	7	24
Homemade Cookies	1	15	10	35
Tailoring	3	27	15	48
Animal feed	2	8	2	8
Coal briquette	1	20	1	20
Welding	6	21	6	21
Ethanol	1	70	1	70
Total	601	1.505	565	1.391

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Takalar, 2013

The data illustrates that for Mangarabombang District there are 19 types of industries with a total of 601 units are able to provide employment for 1,505 people in 2010. This industry is the type that received direct assistances from Takalar Government so it can be ascertained that there are more industries that still have not been recorded. There are two types of dominant industry in the Mangarabombang District, the salt-making industry for 170 units with the number of workers absorbed of 380 people, which means that the proportion of salt-making industry to the total existing industry amounted to 30.09%, while the proportion of labor force reached 27, 32% of the total workforce in the creative industries sector. Furthermore, in the first place is woven pandanus leaves industries for 209 units with the number of labor absorption of 329 people, which means the proportion is 36.99% of the total industry in this region and the proportion of labor absorption is 23.65%

c. Mappakasunggu Dsistrict

Mappakasunggu District is 45,27 km² width which includes six villages and populated by 15,177 people and 3,383 households in 2010 with the density of 335 people per km². This area is popular as the central of pottery producers in Takalar Regency Takalar.

Table 2: Number of Creative Industries in Mappakasunggu District in 2010 – 2011

Industry Type	2010		2011	
	Units	Workforces	Units	Workforces
Pandanous Leaves Plaiting	45	97	45	97
Pottery	239	684	160	520
Bamboo Plaiting	17	72	15	65
Table Salt Production	1	15	1	6
Salt Production	60	131	60	131
Gedogan Weaving	30	40	10	18
Wooden Furniture	2	10	12	42
Bricks	3	25	3	25
Cookies Homamaking	2	10	4	15
Total	399	1.084	310	919

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Takalar, 2013

The data shown in the table above illustrates that creative industries in this region is dominated by pottery industries, which accounted for 239 units with employment of 684 people, which means that the proportion is 60.20% of the total types of existing industries and employment by 63.39% of the total workforce in creative industries sector.

d. South Polombangkeng District

South Polombangkeng District is 88,07 km² width which includes 10 villages and populated by 27,132 people and 6,701 households in 2010, while the density was 374 people per km².

Table 3: Numbers of Creative Industries in South Polombangkeng District in 2010 – 2011

Jenis Industri	2009		2010	
	Unit	T.Kerja	Unit	T.Kerja
01. Animal Feed Industry	1	6	1	6
02. Cane Sugar	3	12	2	12
03. Pottery	73	334	0	0
04. Tailor	13	39	9	24
05. Pandanouse Leaves Plaiting	74	134	74	134
06. Wooden Furniture	16	106	18	75
07. Cement Goods Industries	3	19	5	21
08. Printing	3	14	3	10
09. Bricks Production	22	203	22	203
10. Stove Production	27	107	0	0
11. Gypsum Profile	1	8	2	8
12. Motorcycle Workshop	6	25	0	0
13. Welding Workshop	5	44	7	50
14. Watch Repairation	1	1	0	0
15. Lunkhead (dodol) production	3	5	3	6
16. Photo Copy	2	15	0	0
17. Crackers Production	1	5	0	0
18. Herbal Medicine	1	5	0	0
19. Toughen Roof	2	14	20	48
20. Cashew	20	20	0	0
21. Machinary Repairation	1	3	15	35
Total	278	1.119	181	632

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Takalar, 2013

The data shown in the table above illustrates that the creative industries in the region are also dominated by pottery industries, which accounted for 73 units with 334 workforces, which means that proportion is 26.62% of the total types of existing industries and workforces is 12.06% of total in the creative industries sector.

e. North Polombangkeng District

North Polombangkeng District is 212.25 km² width which includes 15 villages and populated by 45,347 people and 11,201 households in 2010 with density of 216 people per km².

Below table describes that for North Polombangkeng Districts there were 21 types of industries with total amount of 241 units that absorbed 1,333 workforces in 2010. There were three types of dominant industries in North Polombangkeng Districts, which were furniture for 81 units with 573 workforces, which means that the proportion of furniture industries in comparison to the total industries in North Polombangkeng Districts was 32.53% while the proportion of workforces up to 46.36% from the total of workforces in creative industries sector. Furthermore, in the second place was pastry industry for 29 units with 58 workforces, which means the proportion was 11.65% of total industry in this region and the proportion of labor absorption was 4.69%. While the third is brown sugar industry for 27 units or 10.84% with labor absorption 81 people or approximately 6.55% of total workforces in creative industries sector in the District of North Polombangkeng.

Table 4: Numbers of Creative Industries in North Polombangkeng District in 2010 – 2011

Type of Industry	2009		2010	
	Units	Workforces	Units	Workforces
01. Brown Sugar Production	27	81	27	81
02. Cookies/Pastry Production	29	58	20	44
03. Mineral Water	2	120	2	120
04. Tofu and Tempe	9	30	2	8
05. Sawmills	8	23	8	23
06. Gedongan Weaving	12	17	12	17
07. Tailor	7	17	9	24
08. Wooden Furniture	81	573	60	280
09. Mattress Production	8	19	8	19
10. Bricks Production	13	52	32	104
11. Wooden Building Goods	12	40	12	40
12. Welding Workshop	1	32	8	32
13. Stone Crushing Industry	1	4	1	4
14. Printing	4	18	6	15
15. Building Goods	3	12	3	12
16. Sugar	1	80	1	616
17. Syrup Production	2	12	2	12
18. Seaweed	1	66	1	105
19. Chicken Nugget	1	5	1	5
20. Nata de Coco	1	6	1	6
21. Welding	18	68	20	74
Total	241	1.333	236	1.641

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Kabupaten Takalar, 2013

f. South Galesong District

South Galesong District is 24.71 km² wide covering 15 villages with a population of 23,684 people and 5,089 households in 2010 and the density of 810 people per km².

Table 5: Numbers of Creative Industries in South Galesong District in 2010 – 2011

Type of Industry	2010		2011	
	Units	Workforces	Units	Workforces
Yeast Production	9	27	9	27
Wooden Furniture	25	82	25	82
Bamboo Paliting	206	502	206	502
Bricks Production	26	294	26	294
Ceramic Goods Industry	8	59	8	59
Palmiyr Fiber Plaiting	125	492	125	492
Brown Sugar Production	5	15	5	15
Pandanous Leaves Plaiting	4	7	4	7
Wooden Carpenter	2	11	2	11
Tailor	7	28	7	28
Embroidery	15	15	15	15
Welding Workshop	2	16	2	16
Printing	1	3	1	3
Tempe Production	1	4	1	4
Fish Floss Production Ikan	20	30	20	30
Woven Mat	30	30	30	30
Boat Production	2	7	2	7
Community Boat	1	3	1	3
Coconut Milling	1	5	1	5
Total	490	1.630	490	1.630

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Takalar, 2013

The table above described that for South Galesong District there were 19 types of industries with total of 490 units able to provide employment for 1,630 people. Three types of dominant industry in South Galesong District, namely bamboo industry for 206 units with 502 workforces, which means that the proportion of total bamboo industry in the District South Galesong was 42.04% while the proportion of workforces reached 30.80% of the total workforce in the creative industries sector. Furthermore, in the second place there was industrial palmyra fiber plaiting for 125 units with the amount of labor absorption of 492 people, which means the proportion was 25.51% of the total industry in this region and the proportion of labor absorption was 30.18%. While the third was the number of industrial woven mat for 30 units or 6.12% with 30 workforces or approximately 1.84% of the total labor force working in the creative industries sector in South Galesong District.

g. Galesong District

Galesong District has 25.93 km² wide that covering 14 villages which populated by 37,747 people and 8,533 households in 2011 and the density was 1,454 people per km². This region is the division of the two districts, ie South Galesong District and North Galesong District. The area including coastal and inland which connected directly to Gowa Regency in the Eastern. Data about the number of creative industries in this region is shown by the following table:

Table 6: Numbers of Creative Industry in Galesong District in 2010 – 2011

Type of Industry	2010		2011	
	Units	Workforces	Units	Workforces
01. Flying Fish	5	60	5	60
02. Boat Production	12	32	12	32
03. Fish Flour	1	8	1	8
04. Fish Processing	16	38	16	38
05. Wooden Furniture	9	32	9	32
06. Bricks Production	8	26	8	26
07. Ice Cube	1	5	1	5
08. Tailor	8	18	8	18
09. Workshop	6	22	6	22
10. Wooden Building Goods	4	14	4	14
11. Cement Building Goods	2	8	2	8
12. Printing	3	8	3	8
13. Welding	3	10	3	10
Total	78	281	78	281

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Takalar, 2013

The above table illustrated that in Galesong District there were 13 types of industries with total of 78 units and absorbed 281 workforces. Three types of dominant industries in the Galesong District, namely the flying fish processing industry for 5 units with the number of workers absorbed were 60 people, which means that the proportion of flying fish processing industry workforces to total employment in the creative industries sector in Galesong District was 21.35%. Furthermore, in the second place was fish processing industry for 16 units with labor absorption of 38 people, which means the proportion was 20.51% of the total industry in this region and the proportion of labor absorption was 13.52%. While in third place was boat building industry for 12 units or 20.51% with labor absorption of 32 people or approximately 11.39% of the total labor forces working in the creative industries sector in Galesong District.

h. North Galesong District

North Galesong District has an area of 15.11 km² covering 10 villages with a population of 35 583 people and 8036 households in 2010 and the density was 2,355 people per km².

Table 7: Numbers of Creative Industry in North Galesong District in 2010 – 2011

Type of Industry	2010		2011	
	Units	Workforces	Units	Workforces
01. Soy Boiled Fish	42	85	42	85
02. Seaweed Lunthead	5	40	5	40
03. Trawl Making	11	13	11	13
04. Fish Drying	21	23	21	23
05. Wooden Furniture	13	60	13	60
06. Bricks Production	22	195	22	195
07. Boat Production	24	55	20	43
08. Tailor	4	23	4	23
09. Workshop	6	21	6	21
10. Flying Fish Eggs	3	45	2	45
11. Ice Cube Production	1	7	2	13
12. Animal Feds	1	10	1	10
13. Sawmills	1	3	2	8
14. Wooden Building Goods	4	15	4	15
15. Welding	3	10	3	10
16. Cream Soda	1	8	0	0
Total	162	613	158	604

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Takalar, 2013

This area is known as densely populated areas because it is located in the coastal areas so that the creative industries activities in the region is dominated by the creative industries in the field of fish processing management. Data shown in the table illustrates that for North Galesong District there were 16 types of industries with a total of 162 units which able to provide employment for 613 people. There are three types of dominant industries in North Galesong District, namely industrial manufacture of soy boiled fish for 42 units with the number of workers absorbed for 85 people, which means that the proportion of industrial manufacture of soy boiled fish to total industry in North Galesong District amounted to 25.93% while the proportion of labor force reached 13.87% of total workforces in the creative industries sector. Furthermore, in the second place there was brick-making industry for 22 units with amount of labor absorption for 195 people, which means that the proportion was 13.58% of total industry in this region and the proportion of labor absorption was 31.81%. While in third place was the boat building industry for 24 units or 14.81% with labor absorption for 55 people or about 8.97% of total labor force working in the creative industries sector in North Galesong District.

i. Pattallassang District

Pattallassang District has an area of 25.31 km² which includes 8 villages which populated by 34,578 people 8,048 households in 2011 and the density was 1,366 people per km².

Table 8: Numbers of Creative Industry in Pattallassang District in 2010 – 2011

Type of Industry	2010		2011	
	Units	Workforces	Units	Workforces
01. Pottery	3	44	120	380
02. Wooden Furniture	6	25	28	96
03. Convection	5	22	5	22
04. Machinery Repairment	24	90	24	90
05. Culverts Productions	2	8	5	21
06. Welding Workshop	3	12	13	42
07. Stove Production	2	6	2	6
08. Tailor	7	24	8	29
09. Wooden Building Goods	4	15	4	15

10. Printing	4	14	4	14
11. Bipang Cake	1	5	1	5
Total	61	265	214	720

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics Takalar, 2013

The above table shows that in Pattalassang District there were 11 types of industries with a total of 214 units able to provide employment for 720 people. There were three types of dominant industries in District Pattalassang District, the pottery industry for 120 units with number of workers absorbed of 380 people, which means that the proportion of total industrial pottery industry in Pattalassang District up to 56.07%, while the proportion of labor force reached 52, 78% of the total workforces in the creative industries sector. Furthermore, in the second place was the furniture industry for 28 units with the amount of labor absorption of 96 people, which means that the proportion was 13.08% from total industry in this region and the proportion of labor absorption was 13.33%. While in third place was the machinery repairment for 24 units or 11.21% with the labor absorption of 90 people or approximately 12.50% from total workforces working in creative industries sector in the Pattalassang District.

1. Potential of Creative Industries Development in Takalar Regency

Takalar Regency as one of the autonomous regions in South Sulawesi, has potential to develop the creative economy in order to improve regional economy and increase people's welfare. Potentials of creative economy existed in Takalar can be divided by sub-sectors, as follows:

a. Advertising

Special efforts in handling advertising services in Takalar not too prominent. The business of advertising media manufacturing is still largely associated with printing businesses (posters, leaflets, banners, billboards and so on). Advertising agency services and advertising media providers (advertising column) held by local entrepreneurs are also not so noticeable. This is partly due there is no daily newspaper in Takalar, magazine and TV media. Most of the mass media circulating in Takalar are from Makassar.

b. Architecture

The architecture field in Takalar is relatively not improving. The numbers of Jumlah specific companies involved in the field of architecture in Takalar have not been recorded. This condition indicates that the building architectural design in Takalar still depend on architecture agency firms from other cities nearby, such as Gowa, and especially from Makassar.

c. Art Goods Market

The existence of art goods market (paintings, sculptures, ceramics and others) as well as antique goods such as art galleries in Takalar is relatively centralized in one of the region. All this time Takalar Regency is popular as a center of art crafts, especially ceramics, songkok guru, sarong, woven mats, and baju bodo.

d. Crafts

Takalar Regency has have a variety of potential crafts to be developed into creative products with high commercial value and can improve the welfare of community. The crafts include blacksmith craft, bamboo craft, and palm fiber craft, pottery craft.

Pottery craft industry is highly developed in Takalar, even known as the center of the ceramic industries in South Sulawesi. Potential of creative industries (pottery) Kabupaten Takalar is likely to increase welfare and create employment by generating and exploiting the creativity and innovations of individual crafters. The industry of traditional ceramic crafts in Sandi Village of Takalar has been going on in the long time process to become part of the existence of traditional ceramics which is managed for generations. The pottery industry in Sandi village including the empowerment of communities to the surrounding environment as one of revenue sources for the craftsmen.

e. Video and Photography

Video and photography ventures are developing in Takalar, but on small scale, so that have not been recorded accurately by Regional Government. The type of businesses include services of video shooting, photo studio, photography services / photography, and movie rental / compact disk (CD), video compact disc / digital video disc (VCD / DVD). The businesses of VCD and DVD producing are conducted on a small scale, for activities documentation, such as: official ceremony at the office, enterprise and campus, not in the form of production house (PH), which regularly producing the TV broadcast. While the film company has not been developed and cinemas are no longer exist in Takalar Regency.

2. The Contribution of Creative Economy to Community Income

Creative economy in GDP structure does not specifically be a sector or sub-sector so that the resulting production value are included in the processing industry sector. Industrial companies that have been growing and developing in Takalar in general are small industries and households crafts. These type of industries are generally highly susceptible to change from year to year, both the increase / decrease in the industrial production as well as the industry existence itself. However, that was not the case in Takalar Regency, the existence of the industry from year to year does not seem to change.

Table 9: Industrial Development in Takalar Regency in 2008 - 2010

Description	2008	2009	2010
Company	2,229	2,224	2,224
Workforce	7,220	7,168	7,168

Source The Department of Industry, Trade and Mines of Takalar Regency

The number of industrial companies during 2009-2010 in Takalar were relatively unchanged which amounted to 2,224 companies. Similarly, the number of workforces, in the same year which amounted to 7,168 people

When viewed from the distribution, some types of industries centered in specific area. In 2010, salt-making industry was in Mangarabombang District Mappakasunggu District for respectively 189 and 60 units. Pottery industries centralized in Mappakasunggu District and South Polombangkeng District for 239 and 73 units respectively. Industries of pandanus plaiting, bamboo plaiting, palm fiber plaiting were in South Polombangkeng District and South Galesong District.

In Mangarabombang District, in addition to salt industry there are also several industries such as gedogan weaving for 58 unit, 209 units of pandanus leaves plaiting, 39 units of prawn paste industries, as well as animal feeds and coal briquettes respectively for 2 and 1 respectively.

While in Mappakasunggu District there were also 239 units of pottery industries, gedogan weaving for 30 units/pieces and other industries. In South Polombangkeng District there were wooden furniture industry, Cement goods industries, brick Industries, manufacture of stoves, cashew and etc.. Furthermore, in North Polombangkeng District there were sugar, wood furniture, bricks industries and others. Likewise in South Galesong District among others there were brick industries, palm fiber plaiting, embroidery, fish floss, boat building and others.

The contribution of creative industries sector in Takalar is projected from the value of production of goods and services in processing industrial sector. The limited specific statistical data which illustrate the potential of creative industries make it difficult to obtain information regarding real value of creative industries operations in this area. Therefore, as a general overview of, it is indicated the data of creative industries sector production value as follows:

Table 10: The Value of Creative Industries Production in 2007 – 2011

Year	Production Value (Millions of Rp)	GRDP of Takalar (millions of Rp)	Contribution (%)
2007	99,716	1,279,150	7.80
2008	113,826	1,550,676	7.34
2009	125,737	1,837,602	6.84
2010	134,950	2,055,096	6.57
2011	146,046	2,368,106	6.17
Average	124,055	1,818,126	6.94

Source: Takalar in Numbers 2012

Based on the data shown in the table above it can be seen that the production value of the creative industries sector in Takalar Regency has increased from year to year. However, its contribution to the total value of production of goods and services in Takalar continues to decline. If noticed that average value of this sector production in 2007 - 2011 was Rp. 124,055 million and the average contribution to the total value of production was 6.94% per year.

The significance of these data is that the contribution of the creative industries sector to community income is still relatively small, this can be caused by lack of intense efforts by local government to provide guidance and management of creative industries sector, however if it can be well managed then the value production will rapidly increase, which means also may increase the economic value added, increase incomes, and reduce unemployment through more labor absorptions.

Based on carrying capacity analysis of Takalar Regency verily creative economic activities have potential opportunities in Takalar. It can be seen from the geographical position of Takalar Regency which located on Mamminasata area, close to city center, has a diversity of tourism potential, has a community bases

in the creative industries sector which are relatively large, and the diversity of community skills. Therefore, based on field observations results, it can be obtained information that it needs to be mapped the potential areas for the development of regional centers of creative economy in each district and this is combined with the development of tourism potential in this area.

Another thing that needs to be closely observed, according to the research team is the unavailability of adequate database of potential creative people outside government-owned industries under the jurisdiction of Takalar Regency so this area is only known as central pottery producer while other potentials tend to be less developed. Therefore, it is necessary to increase the number of creative entrepreneurs as industrial locomotives in creative economy sector, through:

1. To provide supports for creative entrepreneurs who require ease to start and run their business.
2. To encourage successful entrepreneurs to share experiences and expertises in basic education institutions to higher education in term of Creative Economy Development.
3. To establish partnerships mechanism among creative economy entrepreneurs as a vessel for entrepreneurship training.
4. To perform restructuring of creative economy supporting industries.
5. To perform restructuring of industrial distribution industry that support the creation of industrial clusters and creative economy corridors.
6. To increase local content innovation, to create a competitive advantage through development of creative product design centers and to socialize the market, design, research outcomes, and development of technology which related to creative economy industrial development.

3. The Relation between Tourism and Creative Economy

In tourism sector, the creative industries are the main mover of tourism wheel. The more specific and more creative the products offered by a tourism destination area then the more interested the potential tourists to visit the place. The more tourists come, the more likely the economic value that can be earned then the creative economy will be more increasing. With creative economy, people are expected to be self-sufficient; minimize dependence, to diminish labor mental, create new employments, reduce unemployment, brighten up tourism sector, and increase regional and community income.

In addition to increasing income, employment and gross domestic product, creative ideas based economy is not too dependent on non-renewable natural resources. In other words, environmentally friendly and in line with the needs of reducing environmental damage.

Selain dapat meningkatkan pendapatan, penyerapan tenaga kerja dan produk domestik bruto, ekonomi berbasis ide kreatif juga tidak terlalu bergantung pada sumber daya alam tak terbarukan. Dengan kata lain, ramah lingkungan dan sejalan dengan kebutuhan mengurangi kerusakan lingkungan.

If it's related to tourism, according to Law No.10/2009 on Tourism, which is defined as tourism is a wide range of tourism activities and supported by a wide range of facilities and services provided by communities, businesses, Government, and Regional Government Daerah. One person or more who travel and perform activities related to tourism called tourist/tourists. Tourist can be classified into two groups, namely domestic tourists and foreign tourists. Domestic tourists is Indonesian citizen who travel while foreign tourists addressed to foreigners who do travelling.

To develop tourism activities in Takalar Regency, then a tourism destination must have at least the following components:

1. Object / attractions and tourism attraction
2. Transport and infrastructure
3. Accommodation (lodging)
4. Food and beverage businesses
5. Other supporting services (things that support the traveling smoothness such as travel agencies that organize tourist trips, souvenirs selling, information, guide services, post office, bank, currency exchange facilities, internet, telephone, phone pulse sales, salon, etc.).

However, the results of observation conducted showed that the potential creative economy development as a driver for tourism sector in Indonesia is still not implemented optimally. If compared with the pattern of tourism packages offered in Takalar, creative economic activities have not been included within. One of the potential that can be used as promotional event of creative economy products is the national tourism agenda in Takalar Regency namely "Maudu Lompoa". This event is a nationwide regular event, where many tourists come and see the event, but unfortunately the event is not used optimally to show regional superior creative products, so that the activity is solely for religious tourism activities and not connected with the marketing of creative products from Takalar.

Based on researcher observations, it was found a lot of interesting tourism objects in Takalar which can be connected with creative industries activities, such as for natural attractions Lamangkia Beach, Punaga Beach, Galumbayya Beach, Gusunga Beach, Paria Sea, Sanrobengi Island, Tanakeke Island, Ko 'mara, and Barugayya. As for religious tourism is "Maudu Lompoa" which is already included in the national tourism agenda. However, in these tourism places there are no galleries or showroom at all to exhibit local superior products so that it becomes less attractive because the tourism areas peculiarities are not enlivened by the presence of inventiveness and creativity products of creative economic actors.

Overview of several attractions that can be connected to creative economy products in Takalar Regency:

1. Deer Hunting Attractions;
2. Lapris History Attractions (Rangong Daeng Romo)
3. Topejawa Attractions;
4. Sanrobengi Island Attractions
5. Coral Tanakeke Island Attractions
6. Fort Sanrobone Attractions
7. Culture Aru & Dance Attractions
8. Cultural Maudu Lompoa Attractions
9. Pammukulu Dam & Bissua Attractions
10. Agro Tourism
11. Industry Attractions
12. Sculpture City Tourism Park

VII. Conclusion and Recommendation

1. Conclusion

Based on field study results it can be obtained the information related to the potential of the creative industries in Takalar, the conclusions are as follows:

1. The creative economy or creative industries have potential to be developed and managed professionally, not only as an activity on small scale household industry but also as a leading sector in Takalar.
2. Takalar Regency has diversity of creative industry which is potential to be developed through intensive training, it is evident from the spread of creative industries types in every District, each of which is characterized by excellent products in creative industries sector.
3. The value of the creative industries sector production from year to year continues to increase, however its contribution to total production of goods and services in Takalar still relatively small at only about 6.94% per year. This meant that the Takalar Government through relevant agencies have not make serious efforts to arrange and provide guidance for creative economics sector, whereas the it is potential to absorb more labor and support increased community incomes.

2. Recommendation

Based on study results of creative economy in Takalar Regency, then it can be given the recommendation as follows:

1. There are needs of a linkage or interconnection between tourism sector development in Takalar with creative economic activity development. This is because the pulse of tourism sector is not only determined by the attractiveness of tourism, but also determined by the presence of typical products which can be objected as souvenirs for tourists.
2. Several potential objects to be developed in creative economy sector in Takalar Regency are as follows:
 - a. Advertising through the provision of media such as local radio and local newspapers as well as a special website to market superior local products.
 - b. Architecture, through encouragement to companies that are specifically engaged with planning and design so it does not depend on resources from Makassar City. To see the potential of Takalar Regency who are engaged in the development of regional infrastructure.
 - c. Art market. The existence of art galleries, showrooms for superior local products are needed not only located in center of the city but also in tourist areas in Takalar.
 - d. Crafts, for now it already grown but it requires more intensive training, capital facilitation from local governments, and providing a touch of innovation and new creations to the motives, designs, and packaging.
 - e. Video and photography, need to be better appreciated because all this time there are more community which involved within these activities but in small scale and a lack of innovation.
 - f. Printing, design, and fashion are also important to be developed, to be driven the growth, and given a wider space of products marketing so as not depends on Makassar City.

3. Government of Takalar Regency should be positioned as promoter for creative economy development, through the establishment of a commitment in each related Regional Government Task Unit concerning the coordination improvement facilitating the development of creative economy integratedly. Government of Takalar may include the importance of creative economy development in regional development planning documents, both Long Term Development Plan (RPJPD) and Medium term Development Plan (RPJMD) of Takalar.
4. Government of Kabupaten may provide public space so that groups of people can be more creative innovative for creative economic development, for example: the facilitation of art galleries, showrooms, facilitation of Takalar website for promotion and others.
5. Facilitation of business capital by pioneering relationships with banking and non-bank financial institutions, related with low-interest loan programs or capital facilitation through revolving capital or business incubator.
6. It is required the regional mapping region by establishing centers of creative industries in each district according to respective potential and combined with the tourism development integratedly so that both sectors can be mutually supportive and contribute to regional economy development in general and may increase community income and reduce unemployment.
7. Government of Takalar in the long term may encourage the interest growth of young people to move in creative economic activity sector by making the creative economy as part of local content subjects in secondary schools, especially in vocational schools.

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